

Potential and indispensable high temperature superconductivity in novel Rare Earth Hydrides under higher pressure.

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Abstract

Room-temperature superconductivity has been a long-held dream and an area of intensive research. Recently, Rare earth hydrides have demonstrated the potential for achieving room temperature superconductivity under high pressure which changes the density of states at the Fermi level, electron-phonon coupling. The proposed project consists of synthesis and characterization of new REH_{12-x} [RE= La to Yb] Rare Earth Hydrides in which H atoms are weakly covalently bonded to one another, with rare earth atoms occupying the centers of the cages (H clathrate structures). The clathrate structures exhibit potential high-T_c superconductivity that originates from the large H-derived electron density of states at the Fermi level and the strong electron-phonon coupling which is related to the motion of H atoms within the cages. The profound implications will be stated after an introduction of Rare Earth Hydrides. Additionally theoretical predictions and subsequent experimental observations of high-temperature superconductivity in dense hydrogen-rich compounds will be reviewed.

In Experimental techniques, PPMS-VSM (9T-QD, USA) and Closed Cycle Refrigerator -variable temperature insert (CCR-VTI) and hybrid piston-cylinder pressure cell (~3.5 GPa), Modified Bridgman anvil pressure cell (~ 8 GPa-MB-cell) and Diamond anvil pressure cell (DAC) upto 50 GPa suitable with CCR-VTI, 1.5 GPa pressure Cell suitable for M(T) and M(H) measurements, at low temperature (2 K) and magnetic field (9 T) will be discussed.

Our work will stimulate future high-pressure experimental work on synthesis of these Rare Earth Hydrides with clathrate structures to explore the high-T_c superconductivity and the peculiar

chemical bondings involved. The results open the prospect for the design, and recovery of new high temperature superconductors with potential practical applications.